

ITPS CLOUD GROUP

Justis Mroz^a

^a *President / CEO / Director / Founder of ITPS Cloud Group*

Abstract

Since our inception in 1974, ITPS Cloud Group has gained extensive experience thru our continued involvement in the Online and I T industries as a whole. ITPS has, and continues to provide a wide range of services throughout the corporate sector ranging from small and medium-sized businesses to the large corporate sector, including recognized names in the Oil & Gas industry, Investment Sector, CFL, and Provincial Government Agencies, in addition to extending specialized services internationally to clients in Bangkok, Thailand, and Shenzhen, China (Guangdong). With over 35 years' experience in the I T industry, ITPS Cloud Group boasts a wide range of I T and Cloud Services ranging from Professional Custom Website Design & Development, Advanced SEO Techniques, Secure e-Commerce & Data Management enhancements, Network Solutions, effective Social Media Awareness, results-driven Social Media Marketing Strategies, Custom Hardware Design / Build / Repair and Maintenance Programs, and Specialized Business Solutions custom tailored to address the more complex issues related to establishing & maintaining a solid presence / reputation in today's ever-changing, fast-paced Digital Marketplace, including an ongoing primary interest and quite extensive knowledge specifically pertaining to Big Data, Scientific Data, Data Mining, and their advancements, relevance, and impact of Big Data to the Internet, I T Industry, and Society as a whole. "Over the years, Justis has developed a unique presentation style and dynamic approach to public speaking whether his role involves being featured as a Guest Speaker, Host MC, or both. His ability to relate subject depth and theme to suit the targeted audience, combined with his experience and knowledge in an ever-growing array of topics and subject matter, including but not limited to, Sales Seminars & HTC, Motivational & Self-Confidence Awareness / Development, I T Industry Growth Concepts, and I T-related Technical seminars make him a preferential addition addition to your event. His energy, enthusiasm, and dedication to the subject-at-hand leaves a leaves a warm, positive and lasting impression with any audience." -Anonymous by choice

Today we are proud to say that our continued growth & success is largely attributed to the continued support from our Client base, developed and maintained over the years under his direction, building a solid reputation for himself and ITPS Cloud Group overall.

May 11, 2019